

Rousseau and Yoga: The Roles of Intelligence, Instinct, and Intuition in the Shaping of Consciousness

Guillemette Johnston

This paper is the fourth in a series of studies investigating comparisons between the pedagogical theories and practices advanced by Jean-Jacques Rousseau and the disciplines and beliefs developed in yogic philosophy. The first two studies (Johnston, 2009a; Johnston, 2009c) viewed Rousseau's concepts of *amour de soi* (self love) and *amour-propre* (pride) in consideration of their relation to yogic interpretations of mind, ego, and intellect, and thus demonstrated parallels between Rousseau's spiritual vision and yogic approaches to the self while looking at the fundamental principles regarding religious education that Rousseau presents in *Emile* in light of yogic beliefs. The second study (Johnston, 2009c) also incorporated Alexander Lowen's exploration of the differences between understanding and knowing, along with Jungian theory and yogic theory, to demonstrate how Rousseau's philosophy of teaching is based on methods that encourage both introverted and extraverted experiencing and aim at forming the child's judgment and knowledge in relation to the early development of the body. This approach emphasizes the roles of feeling and sensing as they develop via the physical senses. The third paper (Johnston, 2012) started to analyze the intricacies involved in the use of elaborate faculties such as imagination, memory, and reason, though it did not look in depth at Rousseau's theories on the workings of reason. It began to examine the human mental apparatus and described what Rousseau would consider to be an accurate mind (Rousseau, 1979, p. 203; p. 207), drawing a parallel between the notion of *ahamkar* or ego in yoga and *amour-propre* in Rousseau's works as regards the acquisition of consciousness. (For a comparative discussion of the terms *ahamkar* and *amour-propre*, see Johnston 2012, p. 143.) A common point between the two theories was that both highlight the inflation of ego as a result of inaccurate or inappropriate uses of speech and memory. Yogic master B. K. S. Iyengar (2005), whose writings on yoga inform the current study, expresses it thus: "Communication and memory permit the ego to feed incessantly off the experiences relayed to it by mind. Naturally it puts on weight and falls sick" (p. 120).

Both yogic and Rousseauist theory acknowledge the pitfalls resulting from the overuse or misuse of faculties, which ends up deviating these faculties from their original function of aiding human survival and increasing the development of consciousness. Indeed the problems that Rousseau and yogic philosophy try to overcome are not only the loss of integration while becoming conscious, but also the loss of connection with the inner self^d while trying to establish singularity of awareness at the biological and other levels. Rousseau's approach to addressing this loss is proactive, in that he is describing a pedagogy directed toward the development of a child, while yoga largely looks at a developed "adult" with already formed capacities that must be addressed, confronted, or surpassed to achieve integration. Both systems assume that through mind and senses, the

ego, here defined as the central expression of individualized consciousness in human existence, may achieve a level of autonomy which enables it to distinguish itself from others. This same ego, though, can frequently get inflated and forget in the process that it plays only a limited part in the overall picture of consciousness, since it is only a reflection of the self, or in Rousseauist speak a perversion of our natural, self-preserving passion *amour de soi*. Iyengar (2005) addresses this problem when exploring the notion of *ahamkar*, or what he calls the “I-Shape”: “What is the point of having an individual I-shape...? The most natural answer is simply that singularity of body requires singularity of awareness.... Our ‘I-ness’ is an identifier. We need to identify with a certain particularity in order to maintain biological and mental integrity” (p. 119). But, as Iyengar adds, “The I-shape’s contact with the outer world is through mind and senses. All the treasure and glory and misery of that contact are passed back to ego, which accumulates them and declares, ‘This totality is me’.... [T]he pure single identity succumbs to the disease of elephantiasis, in which our self becomes grossly enlarged, coarsened, and thickened” (p. 119-120).

Rousseau’s concept of *amour-propre*, which originally links with the notion of survival, describes the phenomenon of coarsening and thickening as an opacity or loss of transparency which expresses itself in the paradoxical situation of having to prefer ourselves over others while also, for our own sake, expecting others to prefer us over themselves (Rousseau, 1979, p. 213-214; for a fuller development of this theme, see Johnston, 2009a, p. 164). In the physical world, the world of matter in which multiplicity and difference rule over oneness, identity can paradoxically become reduced solely to the ego or to the concept of *amour-propre*. Yet in a manner close to yogic philosophy, Rousseau assumes that our universal and permanent identity is not contained by the limited concept of ego; hence the attempt at studying how the mind works, and how consciousness and conscience operate. Rousseau undertakes this enterprise in *Emile* by describing an imagined process of developmental education, while yoga (which we examine in this study both through the sacred aphorisms offered in the ancient *Yoga Sutra* of Patañjali (ca.200 BCE-200 CE), a comprehensive guide to the universal practice of yoga, and through the lens of contemporary yogic master B. K. S. Iyengar) elucidates specific disciplines and practices that promote a state of integrity and integration. After clarifying Rousseau’s understanding of the nature of reason, this paper will examine both Rousseau’s pedagogy and yogic practices and beliefs to see how these two systems offer parallel or similar practices and approaches regarding the role of mind and body in the development of the faculties of instinct, intuition, and intelligence, and how these faculties assist in fostering consciousness.

In an earlier study (Johnston, 2009a, p.169-171) we mentioned that if in yoga one has to perfect the withdrawal of the senses, *pratyahara*,² to reach inner objectivity, in Rousseau’s educational system, the senses and their interactions with the outside world are meticulously monitored in order to prevent them from relating distorted knowledge in the first place. In other words, the teachings of yoga rely on a system that addresses all the idiosyncrasies of the mind and the intellect in the present, after the senses and mind have been exposed to the forces of corruption.³ Rousseau’s system, on the other hand, uses a more progressive and linear approach. *Emile* becomes a prototype of the human

whose faculties and functions, with the master's assistance, should develop in such a way that he remains connected to his sense of *amour de soi*, without the interference or pollution of extra, unnecessary knowledge that would remove the child from his center. The mind and the intellect develop synchronically while being put to work only for the benefit of a well-engineered human machine that will not go astray and not get trapped in "confusing patterns of thinking" (Johnston, 2012, p. 120).⁴ Thus if yoga identifies three elements simultaneously at work in the processes of consciousness—mind, ego and intelligence—while associating the workings of mind and ego with the mental body and those of intelligence with the intellectual body,⁵ Rousseau establishes the premises of the child's intellectual and mental development uniquely within the context of nature in the physical sense, for according to him this establishment of a foundation in nature is the only way to keep the child grounded, centered, integrated and satisfied.⁶ It is also the only way to give him a sense of natural freedom in which nature itself delineates for him what freedom signifies in terms of need and necessity, as opposed to desire and fancy linked to the suggestions of memory and to an imagination that is uselessly at work if it is not guided by nature's demands.

Indeed, Rousseau sees three sources of influence in the domain of education: that of nature, that of objects and that of men. The only way to succeed is to submit the influence of things and men to the demands and influences of nature:

Everything we do not have at our birth and which we need when we are grown is given us by education.

This education comes to us from nature or from men or from things. The internal development of our faculties and our organs is the education of nature. The use that we are taught to make of this development is the education of men. And what we acquire from our own experience about the objects which affect us is the education of things.

Each of us is thus formed by three kinds of masters.... Now of these three different educations, the one coming from nature is in no way in our control; that coming from things is in our control only in certain respects; that coming from men is the only one of which we are truly the masters. Even if we are the masters only by hypothesis. For who can hope entirely to direct the speeches and the deeds of all those surrounding a child?

Therefore, when education becomes an art, it is almost impossible for it to succeed, since the conjunction of the elements necessary to its success is in no one's control. All that one can do by dint of care is to come more or less close to the goal.... What is that goal? It is the very same as that of nature. This has just been proved. Since the conjunction of the three educations is necessary to their perfection, the two others must be directed toward the one over which we have no power. (Rousseau, 1979, p. 38-39)

Nature, need and necessity enable Rousseau to avoid the danger that his child will be guided exclusively by the pleasure/pain principle, regardless of the crucial demands of the body. For Rousseau it is by preserving the balance between the demands of the body and the development of the faculties that man succeeds in achieving harmony and contentment: “nature ... gives [man] only the desires necessary to his preservation and the faculties sufficient to satisfy them.... Only in this original state are power and desire in equilibrium and man is not unhappy” (Rousseau, 1979, p. 80).

By limiting the aspirations of the child to the exclusive and necessary demands of nature, Rousseau aims at controlling the functions of mind and intelligence attributed to consciousness as components in gaining knowledge. These functions are also recognized by yogis, who acknowledge that in the processes of consciousness there are mental fluctuations and physical abilities at work. They include cognition, which enables man to perceive, know and recognize things; volition, which gives man “the impulse to initiate action”; and motion, which “expresses the fire nature of the mind” through the natural, flickering mental fluctuations by which “consciousness modifies itself” and shows its “vivacity” (Iyengar, 1995, p. 152). However, if all these fluctuations operate via impulses that no longer reflect the needs of the body, but only the workings of the mind without any connection to the inner environment of the individual and the practical outer environment of nature, one can be led to chaos resulting from the misuse of these functions. Rousseau attempts to remedy this problem by giving the child a practical education based on self-preservation and by excluding any unwanted theoretical applications from his curriculum:

Since man’s first natural movements are ... to measure himself against everything surrounding him and to experience in each object he perceives all the qualities which can be sensed and relate to him, his first study is a sort of experimental physics relative to his own preservation.... While his delicate and flexible organs can adjust themselves to the bodies on which they must act, while his still pure senses are exempt from illusions, it is the time to exercise both in their proper functions, it is the time to teach the knowledge of the sensible relations which things have with us. Since everything which enters into the human understanding comes there through the senses, man’s first reason is a reason of the senses; this sensual reason serves as the basis of intellectual reason. Our first masters of philosophy are our feet, our hands, our eyes. To substitute books for all that is not to teach us to reason. It is to teach us to use the reason of others. It is to teach us to believe much and never to know anything.

To exercise an art one must begin by procuring for oneself the instruments for it; and, to be able to employ these instruments usefully, one has to make them solid enough to resist wear. To learn to think, therefore, it is necessary to exercise our limbs, our senses, our organs, which are the instruments of our intelligence. And to get the greatest possible advantage from these instruments, the body which provides them must be robust and healthy. Thus, far from man’s true reason being formed independently of the body, it is the body’s good constitution which makes the mind’s operations easy and sure. (Rousseau, 1979, p. 125)⁷

Rousseau recognizes that to think adequately, without interferences prompted by the mind, one has to ensure that all instruments that assist intelligence remain unflawed.⁸ He contends that our pure senses are originally “exempt from illusions” and that in order to function well, our organs have to be used properly and be tuned to “the sensible relations which things have with us.” This factor is quintessential for Rousseau, since he asserts that human understanding is molded by perceptions that are the end results of the use of the senses, and by extension of the responses of the body. Besides its attempts to make sure that the senses function smoothly, Rousseau’s method relies basically on a natural sense of self preservation that is not one of the senses *per se*, yet is a basic instinct that provides the main necessary protective mechanism for an environmentally sensitive functioning of the organism.

Thus Rousseau’s theory maintains that one has to monitor the individual’s original relations to the environment within the context of basic survival, for it is this type of interaction, as opposed to reading about and speculating on abstract theories, that forms the background for the development of the child’s simple and complex faculties.⁹ Because it already requires evaluating and comparing situations through the senses, this approach can be seen as forming the premises for the child’s intellectual reason: “sensual reason serves as the basis of our intellectual reason” (Rousseau, 1979, p. 125). The goal of this method is to ensure that the mind of the child not be engaged too early in complex operations involving an overextended and unjustified use of memory and imagination, but only in situations in which need and necessity help form the ground for survival by bringing the child to develop aptitudes and skills attuned to realities that later in life will help form clear judgment. Hence theoretically good common sense prevails over useless movements of the mind and unnecessary relations, no matter how complex the situation. Thanks to this insistence on the deployment of instinct in the early development of the functions of the mind, when more elaborate situations demand the use of complex faculties to serve complex ends, intuitive knowledge will, in theory, take over, enabling the child to act with discernment. Indeed, Rousseau describes the well-regulated use of the senses as the process of cultivating a sixth sense that he calls common sense, one that becomes the main sense in acts of discerning, and that also serves as a reliable tool in what he calls intellectual reason or human reason:

common sense ... results from the well-regulated use of the other senses ... because it instructs us about the nature of things by the conjunction of all their appearances. This sixth sense has consequently no special organ. It resides only in the brain, and its sensations, purely internal, are called *perceptions* or *ideas*. It is by the number of these ideas that the extent of our knowledge is measured. It is their distinctness, their clarity which constitutes the accuracy of the mind. It is the art of comparing them among themselves that is called *human reason*. Thus what I would call *sensual* or *childish* reason consists in forming simple ideas by the conjunction of several sensations, and what I call *intellectual* or *human reason* consists in forming complex ideas by the conjunction of several simple ideas. (Rousseau, 1979, p. 157-158)

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From this understanding we can see why Rousseau argues for keeping the child in tune with nature and his immediate environment in order to assist in the development of his future reason:

if instead of taking your pupil's mind far away ... you apply yourself to keeping him always within himself and attentive to what touches him immediately, then you will find him capable of perception, memory, and even reasoning. This is nature's order. To the extent the sensitive being becomes active, he acquires a discernment proportionate to his strengths....

[H]e judges, he foresees, he reasons in everything immediately related to him. He does not chatter; he acts....

[S]o long as he is concerned only with his immediate and palpable interest, you will witness developing all the reason of which he is capable much better and in a way much more appropriate to him than it would in purely speculative studies. (Rousseau, 1979, p. 117-120)

Rousseau thinks of reason as a composite of all the other faculties (see Johnston, 2012). Thus his highlighting of sensual reason works as a way of preparing Emile for adult reason, in that the emphasis of this teaching is on direct and concrete experience that can be applied at any time. Says Rousseau of children, "they reason very well in everything they know that relates to their immediate and palpable interest" (1979, p. 108).

If in Rousseau's method memory, imagination and language are seldom put to use in the context of the child's world, and if when they are, they are solely applied to his survival, the development of habits is also proscribed from Emile's educating, since "habit adds a new need to that of nature" (Rousseau, 1979, p. 63). This reaction against habit may seem unusually forced, but we must remember William James's contention that "*habit diminishes the conscious attention with which our acts are performed*" and that habit "is not a thought or a perception, but the *sensation occasioned by ... muscular contraction*" (James, 1890, p. 114-115; italics in original). For Rousseau, habit can only make the child more rigid and less open to the needs of the moment. He warns, "The only habit that a child should be allowed is to contract none.... Prepare from afar the reign of his freedom and the use of his forces by leaving natural habit to his body" (Rousseau, 1979, p. 63). Rousseau goes so far as to say that if the child is given a successful education, he will "not know what routine, custom, or habit is" (Rousseau, 1979, p. 160). He details why habit should be considered a vice:

The appeal of habit comes from the laziness natural to man, and that laziness increases in abandoning oneself to habit. One does more easily what one has already done; the trail once blazed becomes easier to follow. Thus it is to be observed that the empire of habit is very great over the aged and the indolent, very small over the young and the lively. This way of life is good only for weak souls

and weakens them more from day to day. The only habit useful to children is to subject themselves without difficulty to the necessity of things, and the only habit useful to men is to subject themselves without difficulty to reason. Every other habit is a vice. (Rousseau, 1979, p. 160)

It goes without saying that Rousseau wants to stimulate and continue alertness and consciousness in the individual. This desire bears close resemblance to similar intentions raised in yogic philosophy. According to B. K. S. Iyengar, consciousness for the yogi “means our capacity to be aware, both externally as well as internally” (Iyengar, 2005, p. 109). In fact, Iyengar translates the second sutra in the *Yoga Sutra*, where Patanjali defines yoga, as follows: “Yoga is the process of stilling the movements and fluctuations of mind that disturb our consciousness” (Iyengar, 2005, p. 108), using *consciousness* for the Sanskrit *citta*. Iyengar thus describes yogic intelligence as “making self-aware choices through informed discernment and the exercise of will” so that we can “initiate change and free ourselves from ingrained patterns of behavior”—i.e., habits—and steer ourselves incrementally toward illumination and freedom” (Iyengar, 2005, p. 108). Iyengar’s—and Rousseau’s—use of consciousness in these passages tones down or moves away from spiritualized understandings of consciousness as “transcendental ... not a product of the finite body-mind, [but] the ultimate identity of human beings” or “the Self” (Feuerstein, 1997, p. 77) that many associate with mystical spiritual practices such as those found in some forms of yoga. Nevertheless, it does link to *citta*, which Feuerstein defines as “an umbrella term for a variety of inner processes, primarily the capacity of attention” that in many yogic traditions stems from transcendental “Consciousness” (1997, p. 74). It thus stands between the yogic perception of transcendental self realization through consciousness and possible western interpretation of consciousness as individualized states of being aware, although one could argue that it comes closer to the Jungian definition of consciousness as “the product of a synthesis between consciousness and the unconscious” (Meier, 1989, p. 3) that nevertheless involves “a distinction between subject and object” (Meier, 1989, p. 9). Either way this interpretation supports both Rousseau’s and Iyengar’s use of consciousness in the limited sense of an awareness of one’s actions rather than habituated response, and Iyengar’s comments suggest a retrospective approach to Rousseau’s attempt to control the growth of habit early on in Emile’s development.

Iyengar also maintains, in a section in which he describes the role of intelligence, that yoga can “help us to truly innovate, to develop the intelligence that allows us to create a new relationship to our ego and our world” (1995, p. 123). He reminds us that the role of intelligence, conversely to that of the mind, which “produces thought and image all the time [but] cannot solve the problems caused by thought” (1995, p. 126), is “to stop, to discern, to discriminate, to intervene” (1995, p. 126). Intelligence, Sanskrit *buddhi*, associated with the intellectual sheath or *vijnamaya kosa* (see note above), thus is distinguished from the mental or emotional sheath (*manomaya kosa*, see note above) which is without *buddhi*’s capacity for discrimination, and must take over the egotistical, individualized self that sees situations from a limited and subjective point of view, since ego (Sanskrit *ahamkar*) is limited by its “pettiness, fears, [and] cravings” (1995, p. 125). Similarly, Rousseau argues for the development of discernment, declaring that

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discernment starts in the proper use of the body, since the body is the basic instrument of our faculties. “[T]he more [the child] makes himself strong and robust, the more he becomes sensible and judicious” (Rousseau, 1979, p. 119).

The difficulties of defining terms such as consciousness, intelligence, ego and so on as used in these contexts should not be overlooked. Arguably, consciousness in the west largely confines itself to a capacity of individualized understanding that distinguishes subject and object, including the “objective” awareness of the self as an entity (a sense of ego) or of aspects of the self as separable content. An eastern, particularly Indian, understanding would see such “individuated” consciousness as preliminary to a larger state of “Consciousness” or transcendent (though not dualistic) Self-realization that in many interpretations unites the individuated self with Godhead. Intelligence, which in the west would refer to a capacity for understanding, in Indian tradition would more describe the capacity for discernment that is preliminary to the distinction of the “Seer” that simultaneously sees, knows, and is joined to the transcendental “Self.” Though the perspectives or approaches to these concepts differ, the difference is more in the underlying spiritual significance applied to these concepts rather than in the operations implicit in the concepts themselves. I would argue that Rousseau’s understanding of these terms approaches closer to the yogic interpretation than does that of many other participants in the historical western dialectic of philosophy. This fact, I would contend, is part of what makes Rousseau so important to the evolution of western thought since the eighteenth century.

With regard to intelligence, Iyengar reminds us that in the overall philosophy of yoga, hatha yoga, the corporeal discipline of practicing *asana* or poses that has become so popular in the west, serves as a basic stepping stone towards sharpening intelligence to make it freer. Practicing hatha yoga involves learning to be connected to and conscious of our outer and inner self. “What you [exercise], along with the components of body, is that too-often dormant component of consciousness, intelligence itself” (Iyengar, 1995, p. 127). The intelligence Iyengar writes of here is an intelligence of the body, a physical awareness of the functioning of muscles or of the coordination involved in certain positions with attention to their effect on the mind, emotions, and body. Reflecting many of the points Rousseau raises concerning connections between habit and discernment, Iyengar describes yoga as a method of freeing us from habit and enabling us to use faculties such as memory not as obstacles that clutter our judgment, but as means to evolve and live properly. Iyengar reminds us that memory is also part of what constitutes the mind, or *manas*, and sometimes, if it is not approached with discernment or *buddhi*, it tends to make us stagnate:

Mind and memory reinvolve past experiences of pain and pleasure and equate them to the present situation, however inappropriate. Whereas intelligence makes creative comparisons, mind makes destructive ones, destructive in the sense that they fix us in a rut, an imprisoning pattern.

Memory is useful if it helps to prepare you for the future, to know whether or not you are moving forward. Use it to develop. Memory is useless if it brings about

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a repetition of the past. Repetition means to live in memory. If repetition is taking place, then memory retards the path of evolution. Do not live in memory. Memory is only the means to know whether we are fully aware and evolving... Living in the past or longing to repeat previous experience will only stagnate intelligence. (Iyengar, 1995, p. 144)

It should be remembered here that if in western tradition memory is largely individualized except in such concepts as “cultural memory,” in yoga memory (at least in its traditional sense) can include deeper factors. As one of the five fluctuations of consciousness that the yogi tries to control in achieving the “stilling of consciousness,” memory can include “subliminal ‘activators’ (*samskara*) responsible for the karmic continuity in one’s life and also between the present existence and future embodiments” (Feuerstein, 1997, p. 291). Though the element of transmigration would certainly not apply in Rousseau’s case, Rousseau nevertheless understood some of the complexities associated with memory, and how active memory could be in preventing clarity of mind. Thus, as we pointed out previously, by facilitating the exercise of sensual reason Rousseau was trying to avoid the pitfalls that memory could generate. His pupil Emile “has less memory than judgment” (Rousseau, 1979, p. 160), and because he is in tune with nature, from the first he is instinctively connected, thanks to the exercise of his sensual reason. Later, he will become intuitively connected thanks to the use of adult or intellectual reason.

In the same way, though even to the point of addressing the organism at the micro level, we can see in yoga a method that tries to direct instinct and intuition to our best use, aiming at complete integration. One of the aims of hatha yoga is to bring awareness to our body, and even, as yogis believe, to each cell. Iyengar writes,

We hear a lot about illumination of the Soul. [Hatha yoga] is illumination of the body. Our cells die by the million every minute, but at least if we bring life to them, they live before they die. When intelligence shines into the cells, then instinct is joined by the higher faculty of intuition. Instinct is memory and mind functioning for good or ill with reference only to the past, life preserving and life destroying jumbled together. When intelligence is awakened in the cells, then instinct is transformed into intuition and the past loses its deterministic grip on us, as our inner intelligence tells us what the future requires.

Memory at the cellular level is at the service of intelligence in the form of intuition. At the conscious level it serves initially as a reference library for intelligence, to be consulted judiciously and with scholarly detachment. When intelligence consults spontaneously with memory at each moment, then conscious intuition arises, and the word we give to conscious intuition is wisdom. (Iyengar 145)

The idea that one can bring intelligence into the cells may seem controversial, as might the idea that bringing this “intelligence” into the cells changes “instinct ... into intuition.” Part of the difficulty with these concepts lies in a cultural context (like that of the west)

which tends to separate mind from body and intellect from intuition, and also to prioritize analysis over synthesis. In the yogic understanding, cellular intelligence is accepted, but from a western standpoint it would be approached from a metaphorical or symbolic perspective, in that it refers to processes that *seem* to affect the body on a microscopic level, but lacks observable data to prove that it does indeed operate in this way. Yet much contemporary mind-body research suggests that cells are central at least to our emotive and perceptual approach to the world, and that they even have a type of intelligence. For instance, neuropeptides and receptors affect awareness and our response to life, with “less than 2% of neuronal communication [occurring] at the synapse. Most communication happens at receptor sites on cell walls throughout the body” (Bragdon, 1998-2001). Dr. Candace Pert, who discovered the opiate receptors through which endorphins bind to brain cells, connects these cellular-level reactions directly to our emotions and intuition, and even links them to yoga, maintaining that “classical chakras areas [correspond to] ‘nodal points’—Places where lots of neurotransmitters and neuropeptides [are] released” (Helfer, 2010). Another researcher, Professor Guenter Albrecht-Buehler of Northwestern University and elsewhere, has conducted experimental work over 30 years that “suggests that single tissue cells have their own data- and signal-processing capacities that help them control their movements and orientation” (Albrecht-Buehler, 2012a). Albrecht-Buehler defines an “intelligent cell” as “capable of collecting and integrating a variety of physically different and unforeseeable signals as the basis of problem-solving decisions” (Albrecht-Buehler, 2012b), and suggests that cells measure space and time, order data, and perform other types of “intelligent” functions. Despite the “New-Age” tone of some of the writing that accompanies and promotes this area of research, there is some evidence for its validity.

Mind-body research also suggests how instinct, intelligence, and intuition might interact. The relation of intuition to intelligence (let alone instinct) has long been controversial in the west. The *Psychiatric Dictionary* defines instinct as an “organized and relatively complex mode of response, characteristic of a given species ... phylogenetically adapted to a specific type of environmental situation” (Hinsie & Campbell, 1970, p. 400) and intelligence as “the capacity to understand and manage abstract ideas and symbols ... to understand, invent and manage mechanisms [and] to act reasonably and wisely as regards human relations and social affairs” (Hinsie & Campbell, 1970, p. 406). In Jungian psychology, which addresses intuition more directly than many other established psychological approaches, intuition stands as a basic characterological function that comes from the unconscious and forms the foundation for first impressions, hunches, telepathic experiences, and other psychic experiences (Meier, 1989, p. 97). At the cellular level, instinct might represent the pure functioning of body parts in conjunction with various body-environmental stimuli such as the intake of food. According to Bragdon, Pert connects these cellular-level functions directly to the intuitive, suggesting that the “cellular information exchange with peptides,” arguably an unconscious experience for most people on the macro level, “is 98% of the biological basis of our emotions as well as ... our intuition” (Bragdon, 1998-2001). The relation of intellect to intuition thus can be seen as involving a dialectic that, taken with the introduction (metaphorical or not) of “instinct” into the cells, clarifies how awareness (an application of intelligence to perception of physiological phenomena) can lead to intuitive response.

Philosopher Henri Bergson contrasted instinct and intelligence by arguing that humans, unlike animals, “are not adequately equipped” (Lawlor & Moulard, 2011) with instinct to survive as animals do. Humans, that is, interact with the world more intelligently than instinctually. But by increasing awareness of the body through yogic or other practices, one might increase consciousness of and even control over instinctive or physiological reactions to the point of impacting breath intake, heartbeat, neurological functions, and so on. This opening to the bodily functions that for many operate at the unconscious level might increase the ability to interact with unconscious stimuli (bodily and other reactions at the subliminal level) that may assist in generating intuition by bringing unconscious or subliminal material into conscious awareness. This increased awareness might then seem to make one feel more “full of life.” Bergson, who was not a psychologist, let alone a Jungian, would have maintained that intuition lets humanity “turn intelligence against itself so as to seize life itself” and escape from the mechanistic or overly self-interested and pragmatic: “intuition reverses the normal working of intelligence, which is interested and analytic (synthesis being only a development of analysis)” (Lawlor & Moulard, 2011). Bergson writes, “in pure perception we are actually placed outside ourselves; we touch the reality of the object in an immediate intuition” (Bergson, 2005, p. 75). This type of insightful and immediate awareness spanning both consciousness and the unconscious may link interior processes with intellectual perception and understanding, generating wisdom.

To recapitulate, both the teachings of Rousseau via his treatise on education and the teachings of yoga as presented in the *Yoga Sutra* (here interpreted and put into practice by Iyengar) aim at developing a greater understanding and manifestation of consciousness, as well as increasing reflection on the modes that foster integration of all the physiological, mental and intellectual levels of the human organism. Above all both aim at maintaining the inner integrity of the individual when he or she is interacting with the outer environment. Despite their differences in approach and terminology, yogic and Rousseauist approaches both look at the components that form the mental and the intellectual bodies or capacities, and try to find out how our physiological body can serve as a base for these attributes so as to enable man to live freely with both conscience and consciousness (*antahkarana* in Sanskrit, literally the “inner instrument” that describes the totality—*buddhi*, *ahamkara*, *manas*—of the psyche [Feuerstein, 1997, p. 26]), which for Iyengar serves as “the witness of the witness” by which we perceive “consequences ... from the deepest level, that of unity” (Iyengar, 2005, p. 178). Instinct, intuition, and intelligence are the main forces driving this process. A careful study of the use of these faculties suggests ways to remedy any lack of sense of unity in them, since their improper use forms the core of dysfunction.

When talking about conscience, Iyengar underlines the fact that conscience is the face of the lens that lets us see things in an introspective way. Because it faces our soul, conscience is less likely to be contaminated by our senses, which usually connect us with the outer world. Iyengar describes it thus: “conscience is the perception of consequences perceived from the deeper level, that of unity. This is where soul infuses matter, a bridge between Soul and Nature. That is why conscience will only ever tell you one thing, offer

one course of action, because it comes out of Oneness. Conscience is consciousness being able to tune in to the promptings of the individual soul (*atma*)” (Iyengar, 2005, p. 178). We can compare this with Rousseau’s philosophy of morals and order that tells us that “[t]he acts of conscience are not judgments but sentiments” (Rousseau, 1979, p. 290) that are directed towards a main center, “which is God” (Rousseau, 1979, p. 292). The notion of unity here expresses itself as a priority given to a whole as opposed to a fragment: “There is some moral order wherever there is sentiment and intelligence. The difference is that the good man orders himself in relation to the whole, and the wicked one orders the whole in relation to himself. The latter makes himself the center of all things; the former measures his radius and keeps to the circumference. Then he is ordered in relation to the common center, which is God, and in relation to all the concentric circles, which are the creatures” (Rousseau, 1979, p. 291-292).

Given the spiritual or religious imperatives suggested by these descriptions of conscience, one may wonder about this term and the phenomena it describes. It seems that for Rousseau, conscience is both instinct and intuition in that it already manifests itself potentially in the state of pure and pristine nature as a natural identity of the organism, expressing a sentiment in the notion of self-protection and self-preservation. The notion of *amour de soi* incorporates conscience and consciousness in their embryonic states, in that *amour de soi* is not inflated by external feelings stemming from the outside, as *amour-propre* is, since *amour-propre* is an outer-directed form of *amour de soi*.¹⁰ Initially, according to Rousseau, we have inborn ways of feeling such as sentiments that are naturally geared for our survival. Among those sentiments, Rousseau names “the love of self, the fear of pain, the horror of death, the desire of well-being” (Rousseau, 1979, p. 290).

Conscience, Rousseau tells us, is a “Divine instinct” that speaks to us in the language of nature (Rousseau, 1979, p. 290-291). One might ask what Rousseau means by “*Divine instinct*,” two words that in some traditions could express a priori opposite concepts. One must remember that, for Rousseau, in the ideal state of nature, instinct has its own integrity in that it works for the good of the organism. Even though it involves operations of the mind and to a certain extent of memory, its function is defined by the urge of self preservation, and in this definite context memory functions in synchrony with the body, using selected and limited resources from the mind to help accomplish acts geared toward survival.

As mentioned earlier, even though the yogic and Rousseauist systems have closely related aims, they tackle them from different angles. For Rousseau, unity and consciousness can occur if nature is well channeled from the start and if elaborate faculties develop proportionally with the needs of the individual. To reach consciousness one has to learn how to think and reason via the experiences of the body, which means that no unnecessary actions or thoughts should interfere with the demands of the environment on the organism. Instinct is gradually assisted by a rudimentary form of reason which puts at work discerning intelligence, an intelligence issued from innate sentiments in a very specific context where operations of the mind do not produce random ideas, but rather ideas that are useful and suited to physiological and emotional

demands. During this process negative education, or “refraining from controlling, directing, admonishing, or cramming the child at every turn” (Dent, 1995, p. 102), serves as a preventive measure to limit any compromising of the integrity of the individual. In yoga, on the other hand, experiencing of consciousness is achieved via a reversed process where one has to rediscover intelligence, intuition and instinct by developing a context where these faculties can operate smoothly without interferences from tendencies within them that uselessly activate the mind. Yoga takes the individual on a path of unlearning and abandoning the unnecessary clutter produced by mind and ego, thereby fostering the sharpening and cleansing of awakening intelligence. It does this by going progressively inwards and cleansing the physical, mental and intellectual bodies. To succeed in cleansing intelligence, the teachings of yoga try to make us aware of what might get in the way of realization.

In book two of *The Yoga Sutra*, Patanjali warns his readers against the forces of corruption, which are described as “ignorance, egoism, passion, hatred, and the will to live” (Sutra 2:3, Stoler Miller, 1995, p. 44). Ignorance is seen as “misperceiving permanence in transience ... pleasure in suffering, [and] an essential self where there is no self” (Sutra 2.5, Stoler Miller, 1995, p. 45). It is interesting to note that some of the sources of human afflictions identified in the *Yoga Sutra* are described by Rousseau as sentiments that gear us toward survival and possibly wisdom. But if in Yoga they cause misery, for Rousseau they are part of the language of nature. “The love of self, the fear of pain, the horror of death, [and] the desire of well-being” are simply passions that need to be harnessed from the start, raw energy to ensure our survival. This energy for Rousseau invokes nature in a state of balance, an encoded system geared at protecting the organism or matter at large. This vision that Rousseau proposes is not naïve, since earlier on he distinguishes between *amour de soi* and *amour-propre*. His preventive method aims to protect his pupil from unnecessary longing for pleasures that would lead to suffering, and from investing too much in the ego or the parts of the individual that might tend to develop pride or *amour-propre*. By assigning the child to a humble position in the order of things, as dictated by nature, and by giving him constant awareness of his limitations in relation to the demands of nature, Rousseau attempts to keep the lens of the self pristine.

Going back to yoga, Iyengar, when discussing the qualities of intelligence, warns us about motivations that may influence our intelligence: “What intelligence does not do well is pick up on its own motivations that are quietly infiltrating from ego” (Iyengar, 2005, p. 177). Intelligence shows such vulnerability because it can be taken over by its conative side, or in other words the side that wills and intends, as opposed to the cognitive side, which reflects. Rousseau’s method similarly works to avoid this trap, but it does so from the start by trying to make sure that the child wills only what is good for him in relation to the dictates of nature as assisted by his common sense. Thus in no circumstance will the child act whimsically, for his behavior will always be both active and reflective as well as tuned to the environment. Rousseau feels that the key to avoiding suffering lies “in diminishing the excess of the desires over the faculties and putting power and will in perfect equality,” for it is “[o]nly in this original state [that]

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power and desire [are] in equilibrium and man is not unhappy” (Rousseau, 1979, p. 80; see also Johnston, 2012).

One of the earlier papers in this series drew a parallel between what Jung considers to be the psychic structure of the individual, i.e. what he calls the subjective factor, and Rousseau’s *amour de soi* (Johnston, 2009c). According to Jung, this subjective factor has to be considered a universal law in the acquisition of knowledge. Its base is the elementary perceptions and cognitions at the core of the interaction of the subject with its environment, which has become or always has been an inborn way of acting. We could say that this form of pre-embedded knowledge presupposes more than instinct, and points to a form of intelligence and intuition. In this respect, both Jung’s and Rousseau’s theories account for an already existing intelligent force playing a crucial part in the development of the individual, whereas yoga sees this force as manifesting itself also as an end result in the accomplished individual, though it reflects back to an ideational context presupposing material reality. Such assumptions about yoga of course can only be made if one looks at yoga as a teaching tool and a discipline, and not as the illustration of a complete system which expresses integration, unity, and wisdom lived in a timeless manner in which the awakened Self manifests Godhead. Either way, both the system espoused in yoga and the system generated by Rousseau aim at integrating the individual with the environment by pointing the way to a harmonious relationship between body, intuition, and intelligence that links one into a higher plane of consciousness.

References

- Albrecht-Buehler, G. (2012a). Cell intelligence. Retrieved from <http://www.basic.northwestern.edu/g-buehler/cellint0.htm>
- Albrecht-Buehler, G. (2012b). Cell intelligence and the future of medicine. Retrieved from <http://www.basic.northwestern.edu/g-buehler/FRAME.HTM>
- Bergson, Henri. (1991). *Matter and memory*. (N. M. Paul & W. S. Palmer, Trans.). New York: Zone Books.
- Bragdon, E. (1998-2001). Cellular intelligence. Retrieved from <http://www.avatarcargard.com/article6.htm>.
- Dent, N. J. H. (1995). *A Rousseau dictionary*. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Feuerstein, G. (1997). *The shambhala encyclopedia of yoga*. Boston: Shambhala.
- Helfer, A. (2010, 26 February). "Chakra talk" with Dr. Candace Pert. *Washington Times*. Retrieved from <http://communities.washingtontimes.com/neighborhood/omkara/2010/feb/26/chakra-talk-dr-candace-pert/>
- Hinsie, L. E. & Campbell, R. J. (1970). *Psychiatric dictionary* (4th ed.). New York: Oxford University Press.
- Iyengar, B. K. S. (1993). *Light on the Yoga Sutras of Patañjali*. London: Aquarian/Thorsons.
- Iyengar, B. K. S. (2005). *Light on life: The yoga journey to wholeness, inner peace, and ultimate freedom*. [n.p.]: Rodale.
- James, W. (1890). *The principles of psychology*. (Vol. 1). New York: Henry Holt.
- Johnston, G. (2009a). Matters of the heart: *Emile* and yoga. In J. Helfer (Ed.). *2006-2007 proceedings of the Society for the Philosophical Study of Education* (pp. 161-171). Bloomington, IN: Authorhouse.
- Johnston, G. (2009b). Rousseau's *Dialogues* and individuation: A Jungian analysis. *PsyArt*. Retrieved from http://www.psyartjournal.com/article/show/johnston-rousseau_dialogues_and_individuation_a
- Johnston, G. (2009c). Understanding and knowing: The yogic language of the senses and of pity in *Emile*. In J. Helfer (Ed.). *2006-2007 proceedings of the Society for the Philosophical Study of Education* (pp. 147-171). Bloomington, IN: Authorhouse.
- Johnston, G. (2012). Rousseau and yoga: Re-evaluating the development of complex faculties as presented in Rousseau's *Emile*. *Journal for the Philosophical Study of Education*, 1, 115-133.
- Lawlor, L. & Moulard, V. (2012). Henri Bergson. In E. N. Zalta (Ed.). *The Stanford encyclopedia of philosophy* (Fall 2012 Edition). Retrieved from <http://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2012/entries/bergson/>

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- Meier, C. A. (1989). *Consciousness*. (D. N. Roscoe, Trans.). Boston: Sigo Press.
- Rousseau, J.-J. (1979). *Emile: or, on education*. (A. Bloom, Trans.). [n.p.]: Basic Books.
- Rousseau, J.-J. (1990). *Rousseau judge of Jean-Jacques: Dialogues*. (J. R. Bush, C. Kelly & R. D. Masters, Trans.). Hanover, NH: Dartmouth College/University Press of New England.
- Rousseau, J.-J. (1995). The confessions. (C. Kelly, Trans.). In C. Kelly, R. D. Masters & P. J. Stillman (Eds.). *The confessions and correspondence, including the letters to Malesherbes*. Hanover, NH: Dartmouth College/University Press of New England (pp. 1-550).
- Satchidananda, S. (Trans.). (1984). *The yoga sutra of Patanjali*. Yogaville, VA: Integral Yoga Publications.
- Stoler Miller, B. (1995). *Yoga, discipline of freedom: The Yoga Sutra attributed to Patanjali*. Berkeley: University of California Press.

Notes

¹ “Self” here should be distinguished from yogic “transcendental Self” with a capital *S*, the realized state of identity of the individual with “the essential core ... of being,” although as Feuerstein (1997) notes, this latter Self “in the Christian tradition is known as the eternal soul” (p. 265). Note however that Rousseau ultimately moves toward a sense of unity associable with the transcendent, though in *Emile* this transcendent is found in nature as opposed to being found in revelation via the Bible. This intention comes out most clearly in the famous Confessions of the Savoyard Priest section of *Emile* (Rousseau, 1979, pp. 266-313).

² *Pratyahara* is defined in sutra 2.54 as follows: “When the senses withdraw themselves from the objects and imitate, as it were, the nature of the mind-stuff, this is *pratyahara*.” Satchidananda (1984), p. 165.

³ The forces of corruption are identified in Miller’s (1995) translation of and commentary on the *Yoga Sutra* as ignorance, egoism, passion, hatred and the will to live. Ignorance, which is the root of the other corruptions, is a misunderstanding of the interaction between the observing spirit (*purusa*) and the phenomenal world (*prakriti*). One of Patanjali’s major aims in the *Yoga Sutra* is to analyze the causes of the error and suffering that are obstacles to spiritual liberation.

⁴ The discussion in Johnston 2012 following this quotation offers a commentary on Rousseau’s perspective on confusing patterns of thinking.

⁵ Mind, ego, and intelligence, in Sanskrit, respectively, translate as *manas* (associated with the *manomaya kosa*), *ahamkar*, and *buddhi* (associated with the *vijnamaya kosa*). Yoga describes human faculties in terms of sheaths, bodies, or (in Sanskrit) *kosas* (pronounced “co-shah”). Iyengar (1993) describes these sheaths as follows:

the layers, or sheaths, are the anatomical, skeletal, or structural sheath (*anamaya kosa*); the physiological or organic sheath (*pranamaya kosa*); the mental or emotional sheath (*manomaya kosa*); the intellectual or discriminative sheath (*vijnamaya kosa*); and the pure blissful sheath (*anandamaya kosa*). These kosas represent the five elements of nature, or *prakriti*: earth, water, fire, air and ether. *Mahat*, cosmic consciousness, in its individual form as *citta*, is the sixth kosa, while the inner soul is the seventh kosa. In all, man has seven sheaths, or kosas, for the development of awareness. (p. 10)

⁶ For a discussion of the meaning of the word “nature” in the context of eighteenth-century European thought, see Johnston, 2012, p. 129, note 14.

⁷ One can compare this emphasis on physical discipline with hatha yoga, a term used for “the vast body of doctrines and practices geared toward Self-realization by means of perfecting the body” (Feuerstein, 1997, p. 118).

⁸ For fuller clarification of this distinction of mind from intelligence, see the discussions of *manas* and *buddhi* in this paper.

⁹ For further clarification of Rousseau’s condemnation of reading in *Emile*, see p. 7 of Bloom’s (1979) “Introduction” to Rousseau. Rousseau’s views on reading are of course highly controversial, but it should be remembered that *Emile* is in many ways a novel and that Rousseau himself condemned efforts to slavishly imitate his educational system. Rousseau of course does not take into account the situation of a child who is “naturally” inclined toward reading. For a precocious child, reading will not affect intellect in a negative way provided that it be geared toward stimulating feeling rather than intellect. Rousseau’s *Confessions* (1995) recounts his own experiences with reading at a very early age (p. 7-8), and this early reading is obviously seen as an instinctive and intuitive experience rather than an intellectual exercise.

¹⁰ For Rousseau, *amour-propre* stems from *amour de soi*: “The primitive passions, which all tend directly toward our happiness ... are all loving and gentle in their essence. But when they are deflected from their object by obstacles, they are focused on removing the obstacle rather than reaching the object; then they change nature and become irascible and hateful. And that is how the love of self, which is a good and absolute feeling, becomes amour-propre.” Rousseau, *Rousseau Juge de Jean-Jacques: Dialogues*, qtd. in Johnston, 2009b.